

STONE MONUMENT ENSEMBLES AND THE CLIMATE CHANGE IMPACT

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DELIVERABLE D 7.5 POLICY BRIEF 1

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The stećci tombstones, medieval limestone monuments unique to Southeast Europe, face increasing threats from both climate change and human activities. Recognized for their distinctive blend of local and European medieval artistic traditions, these sites have been granted UNESCO World Heritage status across Bosnia and Herzegovina, Croatia, Montenegro, and Serbia. However, while UNESCO guidelines emphasize cultural continuity and historical authenticity, they do not directly address climate adaptation. The STECCI project highlights urgent environmental risks—thermal stress, freeze-thaw cycles, and air pollution—while developing innovative scientific and socio-economic strategies to ensure their long-term preservation.

To safeguard these and other cultural heritage sites, comprehensive preservation efforts and robust policies are urgently needed. This Policy Brief outlines the key policy options and recommended actions to address these challenges and ensure the resilience of heritage monuments in the face of climate change and human-induced stressors.

This Policy Brief is the first in a series of three interconnected policy briefs. Policy Brief 2 will focus on strengthening the project's long-term impact and sustainability, while Policy Brief 3 will address sustainable Stećci Tourism. Together, these policy briefs will work in synergy to ensure a comprehensive and sustainable approach to the project's goals.

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1. KEY RECOMMENDATIONS

1.1 Strengthening Legal Protections

Implement stronger laws to protect stecci tombstones from urban development, vandalism, and environmental damage.

1.2. Developing Climate-Resilient Conservation Techniques

It is crucial to fund research on how climate change impacts limestone monuments and apply advanced, science-based principles in their protection

1.3. Integrating Heritage Protection into Climate Plans

It is of paramount importance to include cultural heritage sites like stecci tombstones in broader climate resilience strategies to ensure they are protected from climate impacts as part of national adaptation efforts.

1.4. Engaging Communities and Promoting Sustainable Tourism

Local education programs and sustainable tourism practices can help reducing damage from visitors and ensuring local involvement in preservation efforts.

1.5. Establishing Ongoing Monitoring Systems

Creating a registry to track the condition of stecci tombstones, using technology like 3D scanning and drones, is effective in regular monitoring their status and adjusting conservation methods as needed.

1.6. Securing Funding and Fostering International Cooperation

Funding conservation projects, pursuing international financial support, and encouraging collaboration between governments, researchers, and heritage organisations is instrumental in advancing the protection of cultural heritage.

2. BRIEF INTRODUCTION AND PROBLEM ANALYSIS

The stećci tombstones, medieval limestone monuments recognized by UNESCO, are intricately carved stones that showcase the artistic, spiritual, and social traditions of medieval communities. However, their preservation is increasingly at risk due to climate change—rising temperatures, increased rainfall, and extreme weather accelerate erosion and bio-colonization. Additionally, human activities such as vandalism, urban development, unmanaged tourism, and neglect further threaten these historic sites. Without urgent conservation efforts, these invaluable cultural landmarks face irreversible deterioration.

Cultural heritage sites face a range of threats from both environmental and human-driven factors, putting their preservation at risk. Climate change plays a significant role, with extreme weather patterns leading to increased rainfall and flooding, which accelerate erosion and weathering of limestone structures. Rising temperatures further contribute to material degradation by causing expansion, contraction, and cracking. Additionally, air pollution, particularly from sulfur dioxide emissions, leads to acid rain, which significantly speeds up stone decay.

Human activities also pose major risks to heritage sites. Vandalism, neglect, and theft result in physical damage, while rapid urbanization and infrastructure projects threaten burial sites and their surrounding landscapes. Mass tourism adds another layer of stress, as increased foot traffic and inadequate conservation measures contribute to environmental degradation. Addressing these challenges requires proactive policies and preservation efforts to ensure the long-term protection of cultural heritage.

The degradation of limestone monuments, including the medieval *stećci*, presents a significant cultural and environmental challenge. These 12th-century monuments are at risk due to climate change and human activities. Climate modeling predicts more extreme temperatures, intense rainfall, and humidity shifts, which accelerate erosion and bio-colonization of the tombstones. Local pollution further exacerbates the degradation process. Human activities such as urban development, tourism, and neglect also threaten their preservation.

The STECCI project takes an interdisciplinary approach to address these issues, combining climate science, conservation, digital technologies, life sciences and social sciences. This approach provides valuable data for preserving these monuments over time and making them accessible for education and tourism. Community engagement plays a central role in STECCI's strategy, with citizen science initiatives, stakeholder workshops, and local partnerships fostering ownership and stewardship. By involving local communities, NGOs, and cultural entrepreneurs, the project promotes sustainable cultural tourism while protecting the heritage.

During the first project stages, STECCI contributed to broader efforts to safeguard Europe's cultural heritage from climate risks by participating and / or organizing events such as the EU-funded ARCHÉ project, the Green Cluster, Policy Round Table and Workshop, as described in the Annex 1 of this deliverable in detail. These events and collaboration help integrate climate science with preservation efforts, bringing together stakeholders from academia, government agencies, NGOs, and local communities to discuss how to integrate climate-resilient preservation into national and local heritage policies.

Despite these efforts, gaps remain in policies addressing climate risks to cultural heritage. Many sites, including stećci tombstones, lack legal frameworks that specifically address climate change impacts. The STECCI project, as part of the EU’s Green Cluster on Cultural Heritage, advocates for stronger legal frameworks and more funding for cross-border initiatives, especially in post-conflict and rural areas where resources are limited but cultural heritage is abundant. Through advanced technologies and interdisciplinary collaboration, these initiatives are vital in ensuring the survival of these irreplaceable monuments for future generations.

3. POLICY OPTIONS FOR PROTECTING STECCI TOMBSTONES

The proposed policy options, directly linked to the key recommendations, combine legal protections, scientific research, community involvement, and international support to protect stećci from climate change and human threats, ensuring their preservation for future generations (Figure 1).

Figure 1. The interrelation between recommended actions and policy options.

3.1. POLICY OPTIONS

Strengthening Legal and Institutional Protections

Action: Strengthen national and international legal frameworks to protect **stećci** tombstones by enforcing heritage laws, restricting development near sites, and pursuing UNESCO or national heritage designation.

Benefits: Legal protection safeguards these monuments from urban expansion, ensures accountability in conservation, and deters vandalism and illegal excavation.

Implementing Climate Adaptation Measures

Action: Fund research on climate change impacts on **stećci** tombstones and develop sustainable adaptation strategies, such as protective coatings, moisture barriers, and climate-resilient infrastructure.

Benefits: These measures mitigate weathering, extreme temperatures, and pollution, preserving the tombstones' structural integrity and ensuring their long-term survival.

Promoting Sustainable Tourism and Community Involvement

Action: Develop education programs to raise awareness among locals and tourists, promote sustainable tourism, and involve communities in site management through guided tours, restricted access, and interpretative signage.

Benefits: Responsible tourism minimizes damage, educates visitors, and empowers local communities as stewards of their heritage, ensuring long-term protection and economic benefits.

Establishing Monitoring and Research Programs

Action: Implement continuous monitoring using digitisation technologies and climate sensors to track **stećci** tombstones' condition and detect early signs of damage. Support research on preservation techniques tailored to limestone and site-specific threats.

Benefits: Early detection enables timely interventions, improving conservation efforts against climate and human-induced damage. Collected data informs future preservation strategies and policy decisions.

Increasing Funding and International Cooperation

Action: Secure financial resources for the long-term protection of **stećci** tombstones through government funding, sustainable models, and support from international organizations like UNESCO and the EU. Encourage cross-border collaboration for sharing expertise and best practices.

Benefits: Financial investment supports conservation efforts, monitoring, and ongoing research, while international cooperation provides access to resources, knowledge, and global recognition, ensuring the long-term preservation of these heritage sites.

4. RECOMMENDED ACTIONS

The conservation of **stećci** tombstones requires a holistic approach that integrates climate science, conservation, and community engagement. These monuments are not merely physical relics but symbols of the rich cultural and historical legacy of the Balkans. Their future preservation depends on regional collaboration, innovative research, and community involvement. To achieve that, as part of Policy Brief 1, the STECCI project proposes a series of recommended actions.

Establishing Multi-Stakeholder Collaboration

Action: Form a coalition of stakeholders—governments, heritage organizations, environmental groups, academics, and local communities—to develop and implement a comprehensive preservation strategy for **stećci** tombstones.

Rationale: Involving diverse stakeholders ensures a holistic approach, combining expertise from various fields and fostering resource sharing, knowledge exchange, and effective preservation. Local communities play a key role in ensuring sustainability and long-term protection.

Securing Funding and Resources

Action: Advocate for increased government and international funding (e.g., from UNESCO, the EU, and private foundations) to support conservation, monitoring, research, and public outreach for **stećci** tombstones.

Rationale: Sufficient funding is essential for the success of preservation efforts, ensuring that strategies are effectively implemented and the tombstones are protected for future generations.

Developing Site-Specific Management Plans

Action: Develop tailored management plans for each **stećci** site, integrating climate resilience, conservation, and tourism management, while addressing local climate, tombstone condition, and specific risks.

Rationale: Customized plans ensure that each site's unique needs are met, serving as actionable blueprints to guide ongoing conservation efforts, from protecting tombstones to managing tourism impacts.

Establishing Educational and Public Outreach Programs

Action: Create educational campaigns to raise awareness about the cultural value of **stećci** tombstones through school programs, workshops, exhibitions, and public talks.

Rationale: Public awareness fosters a sense of ownership and responsibility, encouraging local communities and tourists to protect the tombstones and reduce unintentional damage, ensuring sustainable conservation.

Developing and Implement a Monitoring System

Action: Establish a monitoring system for **stećci** tombstones, using technology like drones, 3D scanning, and climate sensors to track their condition and store data on a central database.

Rationale: Continuous monitoring enables early detection of damage, allowing for timely interventions. This system also creates a comprehensive record for future conservation efforts and informed policy decisions.

Integrating Cultural Heritage Preservation into Broader Climate Adaptation Plans

Action: Integrate **stećci** tombstones into broader climate adaptation and resilience frameworks at local and national levels, advocating for their inclusion in climate change mitigation plans, especially in areas prone to flooding or temperature extremes.

Rationale: Cultural heritage is often overlooked in climate discussions, despite being vulnerable to environmental changes. Including **stećci** tombstones in climate resilience plans ensures coordinated efforts for their protection, strengthening their resilience to future climate challenges.

Fostering Regional and International Collaboration

Action: Build international partnerships to share research, conservation practices, and funding opportunities for the protection of **stećci** tombstones, collaborating with organizations like UNESCO.

Rationale: Regional and international cooperation enables sharing of resources, knowledge, and expertise to address common preservation challenges. It also raises global awareness and fosters collective action to protect culturally significant sites, promoting cross-border preservation efforts.

Establishing the European Cultural Route for the stećci tombstones

Action: Based on the mutual learning exercise with researchers and policymakers and the social lab research, establishing a European Cultural Route for the **stećci** tombstones could significantly enhance the preservation and a sensitive valorisation of this unique cultural heritage. By integrating these medieval tombstones into a broader European network, the initiative would promote cross-cultural and transregional dialogue and understanding, highlighting the shared history and values of all dedicated region.

Rationale: The recognition of the Cultural Route is expected to attract more tourists, fostering sustainable economic development, and encouraging local communities to engage in heritage conservation efforts. Additionally, the route would provide educational opportunities, raising awareness about the historical and artistic significance of the **stećci**. Against this background, It is suggested to develop at least one **stećci** route during the project duration to gain a certification as "Council of Europe Cultural Route".

These actions, rooted in the combination of tradition, innovation, and community involvement, ensure that stećci tombstones, symbols of the medieval Balkans' cultural synthesis, are preserved for future generations. Integrating these efforts into broader cultural heritage frameworks will safeguard the monuments while promoting sustainable economic development in the region.

5. CONCLUSION

The preservation cultural heritage, including stećci tombstones, is an urgent matter that requires immediate and strategic action to mitigate the growing threats posed by climate change and human activity. Without swift intervention, these invaluable cultural monuments risk irreversible damage. Policymakers, heritage managers, and local communities must collaborate to implement protective measures that safeguard Europe's cultural heritage for future generations. Prioritizing their preservation today is essential to ensuring that this unique historical legacy endures.

Referred to:

Resolution [CM/Res\(2013\)67](#) revising the rules for the award of the “Cultural Route of the Council of Europe” certification (Adopted by the Committee of Ministers on 18 December 2013 at the 1187bis meeting of the Ministers' Deputies) <https://search.coe.int/cm?i=09000016805c69fe>

[Cultural Routes of the Council of Europe - Homepage - Cultural Routes](#)

ANNEX 1.

Annex 1 describes the key activities within the first 18 project months that led to the development of Policy Brief 1

A1. KEY ACTIVITIES

1.1. KEY ACTIVITIES AND STRATEGIES FOR PROTECTING STEĆCI FROM CLIMATE CHANGE – RESEARCH, STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT, AND ADAPTIVE PRESERVATION APPROACHES

Policy Brief Round table/workshop convened stakeholders to address climate-induced threats to Europe's stone heritage, focusing on limestone monument (stecci primarily) policy integration, technological innovation, and community engagement. Participants reviewed policy targeting national ministries, EU agencies, UNESCO STECCI team members (present at the roundtable), legislative improvements, and strategies for community-driven monitoring and public awareness. These efforts aim to foster local stewardship and institutional cooperation. Over two days, attendees explored climate-related risks, innovative preservation solutions, and pathways to implement STECCI's principles across governance levels. The workshop underscored the urgency of addressing climate impacts on heritage through policy coherence, cutting-edge technology, and grassroots participation. Policymakers were urged to incorporate STECCI's scientifically grounded principles and risk assessment instruments into national conservation legislation, support interdisciplinary research that combines stone conservation with climate modelling, particularly in rural and conflict-affected areas and remote citizen science, social laboratories, and digital heritage resources to enhance public engagement and economic prospects in cultural tourism. This integrated strategy guarantees the preservation of the UNESCO-recognized importance of stecci, which represent centuries of cultural synthesis, in a time when environmental instability threatens their physical existence.

While each country must adhere to its national legislation (as outlined in this document), STECCI simultaneously broadens its influence by forging EU-wide partnerships and internationalizing its framework through UNESCO collaborations. Such as, STECCI aligns with UNESCO's priorities on safeguarding cultural heritage against climate change, contributing to global initiatives such as the *World Heritage Convention* and the *Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)*, particularly Goal 11.4 on protecting cultural heritage. These efforts ensure that STECCI's methodologies and tools for climate resilience are integrated

into UNESCO's global advocacy, training programs, and policy dialogues, amplifying its reach beyond Europe. However, STECCI expands its impact through EU-wide partnerships, notably joining the *Green Cluster on Cultural Heritage*, a coalition of 11 EU-funded projects, and engaging with the EU ARCHE stakeholder network.

Within the Green Cluster, the *Climate Effects Team* (comprising THETIDA, RescueME, TRIQUETRA, and STECCI) focuses on safeguarding monuments and historic sites from climatic and anthropogenic hazards, leverages remote monitoring technologies, predictive modelling, and multi-hazard risk assessments to improve preparedness and conservation outcomes. Complementary consortia within the Cluster develop sustainable restoration materials, advanced monitoring systems, and AI-driven tools to optimize preservation accuracy. By uniting projects like STECCI within EU networks such as the Green Cluster and ARCHE, the EU seeks to harmonize research, policy, and community action, ensuring the preservation of Europe's cultural legacy amid escalating environmental challenges.

1.2. STECCI AND STEĆCI SITES

STECCI is a multidisciplinary Horizon Europe R&I project combining expert knowledge and skills from conservation and conservation science, climate and environmental sciences, life sciences, social sciences, economy, creative industries and humanities to overcome the challenges in the Cultural Heritage realm imposed by Climate Change (Map 1).

Stećci are medieval monolithic tombstones found primarily in Bosnia and Herzegovina, but also in some parts of Croatia, Montenegro and Serbia. These unique tombstones were mainly produced from the 12th to the 16th century (Figure 1 and 2).

Figure 1. Stećci site in BiH (a) and STECCI site in Germany (b)

STECCI Consortium

Map 1. STECCI sites

Figure 2. STECCI sites

STEĆCI IN STECCI

Stećci are medieval gravestones that reflect a captivating era in the cultural history of Southeastern Europe. Correlating these tombstones directly with beliefs, burial customs, and the developing religious heritage of mediaeval societies, renowned for their artistic stylisation and epigraphic inscriptions, stećci attest to centuries of cultural trade and interaction between local Balkan traditions and wider medieval European influences. They primarily originate from the 12th to the 16th century, including several centuries of considerable political, theological, and social turmoil. In spite of these turbulent times, communities in present-day Bosnia and Herzegovina, and parts of Croatia, Montenegro, and Serbia, are marked by these unique medieval monuments. In distant medieval times, inhabitants of these places cultivated unique techniques of stone carving, with ornamental and inscription styles that embody both local customs and wider European influences. The term “stećci” (singular: stećak) has been employed since the 19th century. Although other medieval burial practices were prevalent across Europe, stećci are distinguished by their significant quantity, varied shapes, and profound symbolism. Archaeologists and historians have recorded more than 70,000 instances across around 3,300 locations. For ages, these stone memorials have been dispersed over rural landscapes, adjacent to forests, atop hills, or alongside highways, silently attesting to the lives, beliefs, and artistic sensibilities of medieval communities.

1.3. GEOGRAPHIC DISTRIBUTION AND LOCATIONS

Stećci are located in multiple areas of Southeastern Europe, with the highest concentration situated in present-day Bosnia and Herzegovina, which contains the majority of these tombstones. Significant clusters are also present in Croatia, Montenegro, and Serbia, illustrating how medieval boundaries and cultural interactions beyond contemporary state limits.

Principal municipalities and locations compiles:

1. Bosnia and Herzegovina: Stolac, Konjic, Nevesinje, Jablanica, Livno, Sokolac, Rogatica, Trebinje, among others.
2. Croatia: Cista Provo (Split-Dalmatia County), Konavle (Dubrovnik-Neretva County).
3. Montenegro: Nikšić, Municipalities of Žabljak and Plužine.
4. Serbia: Bajina Bašta, Prijepolje, and adjacent regions.

The terrains upon which these tombstones are situated are similarly varied. Certain locations are positioned on hills to capitalise on breath-taking vistas, whereas others are situated in valleys, woodlands, or agricultural landscapes. Some stećci graves are located near medieval churches or earlier prehistoric

structures, indicating a sustained human presence over many centuries. The juxtaposition of many epochs in a single location frequently enhances their historical and cultural significance.

1.4. SIGNIFICANCE IN ART AND CULTURE

Each stećak is often sculpted from indigenous stone, predominantly limestone, although alternative materials such as serpentine or slate are frequently observed. They are available in various primary forms:

1. Slab: Typically, flat and rectangular in shape.
2. Chest: A more volumetric, cuboidal structure.
3. Gabled Roof (Sljemenjak): Similar to a little house roof.
4. Monumental Cross: Limited in quantity but distinguished by their substantial cross form.
5. Pillar: Vertical stones characterised by rectangular or columnar shapes.

Some stećci are embellished with bas-relief or gravure designs, including crosses, spirals, solar or lunar symbols, animal representations, and highly stylised human forms involved in dancing or hunting. These designs integrate iconography with traditional local motifs. In several instances, inscriptions elucidate familial connections, social standing, or personal communications from the deceased or their relatives, providing essential insights for historians endeavouring to reconstruct medieval life and cultural activities.

1.5. NOMINATION FOR UNESCO WORLD HERITAGE (NO. 1504)

Due to their distinctive combination of local creative traditions and wider medieval European influences, several stećci cemeteries were nominated for UNESCO World Heritage status by four states parties: Bosnia and Herzegovina, Croatia, Montenegro, and Serbia.

A total of 28 sites, encompassing over 4,100 tombstones, were selected to exemplify the diverse array of shapes, decorative styles, inscriptions, and geographic locations, using the following rationale for exceptional universal significance:

1. Criterion (iii) – Outstanding evidence of a cultural tradition: The stećci exemplify a lost medieval burial practice unique to this region of Europe. They convey significant insights into feudal relations, religious variety (including Catholic, Orthodox, and other Christian groups), and local cultural dynamics.
2. Criterion (vi) – Pertaining to beliefs and practices: Although less highlighted in later assessments, the tombstones are intimately connected to the region's medieval beliefs, burial customs, and developing social systems.

ICOMOS Technical Assessment and Mission Conclusions from September 2015 to January 2016, international specialists from ICOMOS (International Council on Monuments and monuments) undertook evaluation missions, assessing nearly all of the nominated monuments.

The following criteria were evaluated:

- **Authenticity and Integrity:** The tombstones' original structures, inscriptions, and positioning within their historical context have predominantly been preserved.
- **Borders and Buffer Zones:** The States Parties modified specific borders to guarantee that each stećak field and its vicinity were sufficiently safeguarded from urban encroachment or environmental hazards.
- **State of Conservation:** Numerous stones are affected by natural weathering, lichen proliferation, and physical deterioration (e.g., fragmentation or impacts from agricultural and infrastructural developments). Conservation practices differ by location, influenced by each nation's resource availability and the dedication of local authorities or communities.

ICOMOS determined that stećci demonstrate significant cultural continuity, connecting ancient pre-Christian practices with medieval Christian influences. These findings endorsed inscription while also promoting more collaborative management and conservation to protect these treasures for future generations. Although UNESCO designation underscores their Outstanding Universal Value, it does not solely protect them from increasing climate-related threats. The STECCI project brings together climate scientists, cultural conservators, economists, and social innovators to develop a science-based, community-focused framework for the protection of stone monuments under climatic uncertainty. This Policy Brief delineates STECCI's approach, encapsulates principal findings, and presents pragmatic recommendations for policymakers aiming to incorporate cultural heritage protection into broader climate adaption efforts.

1.6. THE STECCI METHOD

UNESCO guidelines generally prioritise cultural continuity, historical authenticity, and community involvement, rather than direct climate adaptation. However, STECCI addresses this issue by emphasising the environmental factors jeopardising the survival of monuments - thermal stress, freeze-thaw cycles, and air pollution—and devising novel solutions at both scientific and socio-economic dimensions.

CLIMATE-FOCUSED CONSERVATION

STECCI's primary focus is to analyse the impact of climate change on the degradation of limestone monuments. The project primarily concentrates on stećci, however numerous findings will be relevant to limestone heritage in other contexts, including Gothic cathedrals, classical remains, and country chapels throughout Europe.

The consortium's multidisciplinary team integrates:

- Climate science to project future scenarios (short term: 2021–2040, medium term: 2041–2060, long term: 2061–2100).
- Conservation and Material Science to examine stone weathering
- Social innovation and local engagement to guarantee that citizen science, stakeholder workshops, and cultural tourism strategies foster both ownership and economic advantages for local communities.

INTERDISCIPLINARY APPROACH

Advanced Climate Modelling with High Resolution Within Work Package (WP) 2, STECCI refines global climate models to a resolution of 10 x 10 km, concentrating on IPCC SSP2-4.5 (moderate) and SSP5-8.5 (high emissions) scenarios. The interactive STECCI Atlas will be developed by data from EURO-CORDEX, ERA5-Land, and COPERNICUS. This WP also links in dose–response correlations between environmental elements and stone degradation, constituting the empirical foundation of STECCI's impending Preservation Guidelines.

Within WP3 team perform *in situ* optical inspections, tests of water absorption, colour and gloss measurements, ultrasonic pulse velocity assessments, reflectance transformation imaging (RTI), and UV fluorescence imaging to accurately delineate cracks, exfoliation, and biological proliferation. Limestone "sensor" probes were installed at STECCI sites to measure deterioration rates under established microclimatic conditions and pollution levels. To get a more precise insight into the way and rate of stone surface changes such as recession, change of morphology, bio- colonization and soiling, changes on these sensors will be analysed periodically during the project's duration. As for *in situ* conservation, STECCI coordinates restorative measures in necropolises in Kopošići and Križevići, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Cista Velika and Split, Croatia.

Digital Innovation and Civic Engagement (WP4) utilises photogrammetry, laser scanning, and economical smartphone-based techniques to generate 3D models of tombstones and whole necropolises, archiving endangered cultural artefacts in digital repositories (Mendeley Data, Sketchfab) to reduce the risk of abrupt

loss due to catastrophic occurrences, examining alterations in stone surfaces over time and engaging the public with virtual reality tours, online exhibitions, and interactive games that emphasise the historical and artistic importance of stećci.

Community-Centric Impact Strategies and Economic Assessment (WP5 and WP6) emphasise the social and economic aspects of cultural conservation. Across partner countries, social laboratories aimed to unite local authorities, NGOs, cultural entrepreneurs, and people to identify cultural tourism potential, formulate narrative strategies, and collaboratively design monitoring frameworks. Concurrently, economic toolkits are being used to analyse cost-benefit assessments for immediate versus delayed interventions, including surveys on willingness to pay, which reflect the valuation of stećci by local inhabitants and visitors. Additionally, sustainable tourism frameworks will be incorporated, integrating both tangible and intangible historical resources.

1.7. ESSENTIAL RECOMMENDATIONS INTEGRATE CLIMATE ADAPTATION INTO HERITAGE LEGISLATION

National and municipal governments ought to amend cultural heritage legislation to mandate climate risk assessments and ongoing monitoring for all stone monuments, especially those designated by UNESCO.

EMPHASIS ON EVIDENCE-BASED CONSERVATION

Governments and cultural ministries can utilise STECCI's dose–response data and *in situ* testing of green methodologies to revise standard restoration techniques. This guarantees a small ecological footprint and economically efficient interventions.

Most importantly, policymakers, governments and cultural ministries should adopt science-based Preservation Guidelines and incorporate STECCI's Preservation Guidelines into national and regional cultural heritage policies to guarantee the sustainable management of limestone monuments in the context of climate change.

Governments and cultural ministries should support funding initiatives for cross-border and regional partnerships that merge climate science with heritage protection. This is especially crucial in post-conflict or rural areas where resources are limited but cultural heritage is abundant. Efforts should also focus on enhancing local expertise through citizen science and effectively communicating any immediate hazards. This community-driven strategy expands the project's data pool.

Apart from that, they should advocate for sustainable cultural tourism, formulating transregional cultural tourism policies that utilise *stećci* and analogous monuments as catalysts for economic development, especially in rural and isolated regions.

Policymakers also should improve digital accessibility, focusing on the digitisation of endangered cultural assets, employing cost-effective technology to ensure broad access and preservation.

A 2. STECCI IN GREEN CLUSTER

While the EU does not have a single, unified cultural heritage protection law, especially not related to climate change, it has developed a robust framework of directives, funding programs, and initiatives that address cultural heritage conservation in conjunction with environmental and climate policies. These frameworks provide a solid foundation for projects like STECCI, which aim to safeguard stone heritage sites like the *stećci necropolises*.

The eleven projects selected for the EU funding have been encouraged to form the Green Cluster on Cultural Heritage. Within the Green Cluster, the "Climate Effects" Team, currently composed of four active EU projects (THETIDA, RescueME, TRIQUERTA and STECCI), has an overarching aim to address the urgent need to protect monuments, historic buildings, and sites from the diverse impacts of climatic risks, natural and anthropogenic hazards. This is expected to contribute to the conservation and protection of Europe's heritage by exploiting cutting-edge remote monitoring technologies and modelling tools for multi-hazard risk understanding and better preparedness. Research within the Green Cluster is complemented by other consortia that develop sustainable methodologies, materials and techniques for the preservation and restoration of art objects and explore the use of advanced and sophisticated technologies for more accurate, targeted, and reliable remote monitoring purposes. The impact of scientific research is furthermore amplified by the active involvement of Artificial Intelligence tools, a wide range of community groups, stakeholders, and participants covering the full spectrum of ongoing research activities.

This includes participatory and inclusive approaches, such as citizen science and participatory Living Lab methodologies. The overall goal of the EC is to support transdisciplinary joint efforts of researchers to develop sustainable preservation and adaptation plans, and to bring community involvement and inclusiveness to the forefront of large collaborative research projects funded by the EU (Gerakis et al 2024). The first STECCI Newsletter was released in December 2024, informing about STECCI participation in the Green Cluster (Green Cluster STECCI Newsletter).

A 3. STECCI IN EU ARCHE

STECI WP2 were presented in actively involved in two-day RESILIENT CULTURAL HERITAGE IN TIMES OF CLIMATE CRISIS EU ARCHE (Alliance for Research on Cultural Heritage) Stakeholder Workshop Berlin, April 16th - 17th, 2024, chaired by Prof. Dr. Stefan Simon, SPK at Kulturforum Berlin, Staatliche Museen zu Berlin – Preußischer Kulturbesitz (published in the second STECCI Newsletter - EU ARCHE STECCI newsletter).

What is European Alliance for Research and Innovation in Cultural Heritage (ARCHE)?

Changes in the political, technological, socio-economic, and ecological landscape impact research and innovation in the field of cultural heritage. These new challenges urgently require solutions for efficient protection, conservation, and restoration, the introduction of environmentally friendly technologies, advancements in digitization, as well as the creation of growth and new jobs in the cultural heritage sector. The ARCHE is a three-year EU-funded Horizon project aimed at developing a strategic research and innovation agenda for cultural heritage in Europe. The project consortium, consisting of 24 partners from 18 countries, is led by the Fondation des Sciences du Patrimoine (France) and started in September 2022. ARCHE, along with other multi-partner projects such as the Joint Programming Initiative on Cultural Heritage and Global Change (JPI-CH), in which the head of the RF Germany serves as the national delegate, also lays the groundwork for the EU's Resilient Cultural Heritage (RCH) partnership. The goal of the RCH partnership is twofold: to strengthen the means for preserving European cultural heritage and to contribute to climate neutrality in other sectors by advancing traditional and innovative practices, techniques, and materials from cultural heritage research. The RCH is the first partnership on cultural heritage to be approved under Cluster 2.

A 4. STECCI POLICY ROUNDTABLE WP7 / WORKSHOP WP5 IN NOVI SAD, DECEMBER 2ND - 3RD, 2024

An important event exemplifying STECCI's interdisciplinary and collaborative principles is the forthcoming Policy Round Table and Workshop in Novi Sad, Serbia, at Matica Srpska (Figure 3) —one of the oldest cultural-scientific institutions in the Serbian language. It was held in December 2nd - 3rd, 2024. The workshop was chaired by Prof. Dr. Snežana Radulović (UNSPMF WP7), Mag Pamela Bartar (ZSI WP5) and the Project Coordinator Prof. Dr. Nusret Drešković (Figure 4).

Figure 3. Matica srpska in Novi Sad

Figure 4. Workshop (a), roundtable and exhibition in Matica Srpska (b)

The Matica srpska (Latin: *Matrix Serbica*) is the oldest Serbian language independent, non-profit, non-governmental and cultural-scientific Serbian national (Figure 4). Founded on June 1, 1826, in Pest (now Budapest) by Serbian legislator Jovan and other leaders of the Serbian Revolution, the Matica moved to Novi Sad in 1864 and is the world's oldest national matrix.

Aims of the roundtable were as follows:

1. To facilitate interproject coaching: Demonstrate STECCI's collaboration with other cultural heritage and climate initiatives in Southeastern Europe and.
2. To establish a forum for discourse among archaeologists, conservation scientists, politicians, community representatives, and creative entrepreneurs. Institute of Archaeology Belgrade were presenting the Creative Europe project "StećakLand: Interpreting Mysterious Medieval Stećak Tombstones through VR". And the Faculty of Philosophy, University of Belgrade, presenting on the ERC project "*Unde venis?*" Investigating the mystery of stećci tombstones.
3. To facilitate Policy Discourse: Produce implementable recommendations for integrating STECCI's monitoring techniques and Preservation Guidelines into local, national, and EU legislation.
4. To encourage creative involvement: Showcase student-created stećci replicas Exhibition and interpretive art related to stećci, emphasising methods to involve local youth and artists in heritage advocacy (Stećci Model Exhibition presented by students of Bogdan Šuput High School of Art, Figure 6).
5. To facilitate Transnational Networking.
6. To Introduce Storytelling in Heritage Interpretation.
7. To promote STECCI in GREEN CLUSTER.

A 4.1. ROUND TABLE PARTICIPANTS

The round table event involved participants from academia, research institutes, government agencies, policy makers, master students and high school students from 4 countries (Bosnia and Herzegovina, Montenegro, Austria, Serbia).

STECI partner participants:

Prof. Dr. Nusret Drešković (UNSA, COO), Dr. Bojana Mališić (UDG), Gabor Szudi (ZSI) Prof. Dr. Goran Anačkov (UNSPMF/ Matica srpska), Dr. Maja Novković (UNSPMF), Prof. Dr. Željko Popović (UNSPMF), Jelica Simeunović (UNSPMF), Dr. Branka Radulović (UNSPMF), Prof. Dr. Maja Stojanović (UNSPMF), Božidar Radulović (UNSPMF)

Policymakers/stakeholders:

UNESCO Stećci nomination team member **Mag Maja Đorđević**, Republički zavod za zaštitu spomenika kulture – Beograd / National institute for cultural heritage preservation, Belgrade.

The National Institute for Cultural Heritage Preservation in Belgrade is dedicated to the protection, conservation, and restoration of the city's historical and architectural heritage. Since its establishment in 1960, the institute has played a pivotal role in identifying, documenting, and safeguarding significant cultural sites, ensuring their preservation for future generations. Its responsibilities encompass heritage protection, scientific research, restoration initiatives, and the integration of conservation principles into urban planning.

Dr. Emina Zečević, National Museum in Belgrade, Serbia, Department of medieval archaeology. The National Museum in Belgrade, Serbia, houses a dedicated Department of Medieval Archaeology, which focuses on the study, preservation, and interpretation of medieval material culture from the territory of Serbia and the broader Balkan region. This department conducts archaeological research, excavations, and analyses of artifacts, including medieval fortifications, churches, necropolises, and everyday objects that shed light on social, economic, and cultural aspects of life during the Middle Ages.

Its collection includes significant relics such as jewelry, weaponry, ceramics, and religious artifacts, many of which contribute to the understanding of Serbia's medieval statehood, trade networks, and artistic influences. Through exhibitions, academic research, and conservation efforts, the department plays a key role in preserving and promoting Serbia's medieval heritage, ensuring its accessibility for both scholars and the public.

A 4.2. INTERPROJECT COACHING:

Dr. Milica Radišić, Institute of Archaeology Belgrade, Creative Europe project StećakLand: Interpreting Art of Mysterious Medieval Stećak Tombstones through Virtual Reality, coordinated by DIGI.BA, Bosnia & Herzegovina 11:40-12:00

Prof. Dr. Monika Milosavljević, Faculty of Philosophy, University of Belgrade, "*Unde venis?*" Unravelling the enigma of the stećci tombstones. The European Research Council project coordinated by ZRC SAZU Institute of Archaeology, Slovenia - with main goal to understand the social life of society that left us these remarkable monuments.

The workshop participants discussed a series of policy papers aimed at national ministries, EU agencies, UNESCO and local authorities. Participants delineated pathways for collaborative financing proposals and

legislative enhancements and stressed the importance of strategies for community-driven monitoring and public awareness initiatives will promote local stewardship. STECCI team presented ongoing enhancement of GIS-based mapping, 3D scanning, and VR/AR experiences to facilitate teaching, tourism, and scientific evaluation, Over the course of two days, participants acquired direct knowledge of the intricacies of climate-induced threats affecting stone heritage, explored new solutions, and deliberated on the implementation of STECCI's principles at various administrative levels.

A 4.3. STECCI EXHIBITION HIGH SCHOOL OF ART AND DESIGN BOGDAN ŠUPUT, NOVI SAD, SERBIA

Figure 5. STECCI Exhibition (a and b)

The tour of the Petrovaradin Castle Museum (Figure 6) was organized on the first day of the workshop, followed by an excursion to stećci exhibit locations in Belgrade, which included visits to the Ethnographic Museum and Kalemegdan Castle on the second day (Figure 7-10).

Figure 6. Excursion to Petrovaradin castle Novi Sad, led by Vuk Radulović, a historian.

Figure 7. Ethnographic Museum Belgrade.

Figure 8. Excursion to the Ethnographic Museum Belgrade led by archeologists Dr M. Radišić (a and b).

Figure 9. Belgrade Kalemegdan Castle

Figure 10. Excursion to Belgrade Kalemegdan Castle led by archeologists Dr Emina Zečević and Dr Milica Radišić.

A 4.4. POLICY ROUNDTABLE NOVI SAD RECOMMENDATIONS

It was recognised that stećci are not merely solitary tombstones dispersed around the landscape; they are significant cultural symbols that encapsulate centuries of Southeast European history, spirituality, and artistry. Attaining UNESCO World legacy designation, these sites have become symbols of the collective legacy of four Balkan states. It was also acknowledged that they evoke a medieval era characterised by cross-cultural interactions - East converges with West, ancient traditions blend with contemporary forms—and demonstrate how art and burial practices can provide deep insights into the human experience. The future conservation of these monuments will rely on strong regional cooperation, active local communities, and innovative research that addresses contemporary concerns. The preservation of stećci exemplifies the effective protection of historical treasures through collaboration and dedication, guaranteeing that future generations can appreciate this lasting legacy of the mediaeval Balkans. By integrating UNESCO's criteria with stringent climate science and community-oriented strategies, STECCI provides a comprehensive approach to safeguarding medieval limestone tombstones from climate change. The project's Preservation Guidelines, shaped and informed by *in situ* experimentation, economic modelling, digitisation, and grassroots engagement, demonstrate the convergence of local knowledge and international norms in effective, sustainable heritage policies.

Policymakers were urged to:

1. Incorporate STECCI's scientifically grounded principles and risk assessment instruments into national conservation legislation.
2. Support interdisciplinary research that combines stone conservation with climate modelling, particularly in rural and conflict-affected areas.
3. Promote citizen science, social laboratories, and digital heritage resources to enhance public engagement and economic prospects in cultural tourism. This integrated strategy guarantees the preservation of the UNESCO-recognized importance of stećci, which represent centuries of cultural synthesis, in a time when environmental instability threatens their physical existence.

Through the integration of tradition and innovation, STECCI demonstrates that cultural heritage can serve as both a guardian of the past and a driver for a more inclusive, sustainable future.

A 4.5. ROUNDTABLE CONCLUSIONS

By merging climate science, conservation technology, and community-driven strategies, STECCI pioneers a multidisciplinary framework to address thermal stress, weathering, and pollution through advanced modeling, *in situ* interventions, and digital preservation. Its recommendations - integrating climate risk assessments into heritage policies, fostering cross-border collaboration, and empowering local stewardship via citizen science and sustainable tourism - highlight the synergy of innovation and tradition.

DELIVERABLE 7.5 POLICY BRIEF 1

As these tombstones face irreversible degradation, STECCI exemplifies how science, policy, and public engagement can transform cultural heritage into a resilient legacy. By bridging historical preservation with climate adaptation, the project not only protects a vanishing medieval narrative but also charts a path for inclusive, sustainable futures where heritage serves as both a testament to human ingenuity and a catalyst for collective resilience in an era of environmental uncertainty.

REGISTER OF INSTITUTIONS RESPONSIBLE FOR STEĆCI CONSERVATION

Each country involved in the STECCI project has dedicated institutions responsible for the preservation and management of *stećci* and other cultural heritage sites. These institutions play a crucial role in ensuring the long-term sustainability of these monuments.

BOSNIA AND HERZEGOVINA

- Komisija za očuvanje nacionalnih spomenika BiH (Commission to Preserve National Monuments of Bosnia and Herzegovina), Website: <http://www.aneks8komisija.com.ba/>
- Zavod za zaštitu kulturno-historijskog i prirodnog naslijeđa (Institute for the Protection of Cultural, Historical, and Natural Heritage), Website: <https://kons.gov.ba/>

CROATIA

- Ministarstvo kulture Republike Hrvatske (Ministry of Culture of the Republic of Croatia), Website: <https://www.min-kulture.hr/>
- Hrvatski restauratorski zavod (Croatian Conservation Institute): Website: <https://www.h-r-z.hr/>

MONTENEGRO

- Ministarstvo kulture i medija Crne Gore (Ministry of Culture and Media of Montenegro), Website: <https://www.gov.me/>
- Centar za konzervaciju i arheologiju (Centre for Conservation and Archaeology), Website: <https://www.cipmontenegro.me/>

SERBIA

- Zavod za zaštitu spomenika kulture Srbije (Institute for the Protection of Cultural Monuments of Serbia), Website: <https://heritage.gov.rs/>
- Narodni muzej u Beogradu (National Museum in Belgrade), Website: <https://www.narodnimuzej.rs/>

NON STEĆCI PARTNER COUNTRIES

- Mdina Rabat (Malta): Managed by Heritage Malta, Website: <https://heritagemalta.org/>
- Unsleben (Germany): Overseen by Bayerisches Landesamt für Denkmalpflege (Bavarian State Office for Monument Preservation), Website: <https://www.blfd.bayern.de/>

- Caen (France): Managed by Direction Régionale des Affaires Culturelles (DRAC) Normandie (Regional Directorate of Cultural Affairs Normandy), <https://www.culture.gouv.fr/Regions/Drac-Normandie>

REGISTER OF LAWS AND POLICIES RELATED TO CULTURAL HERITAGE PROTECTION AND CLIMATE CHANGE THREATS BY COUNTRY

BOSNIA AND HERZEGOVINA

- Law on the Protection of Cultural, Historical, and Natural Heritage (Federation of BiH): <http://www.fbihvlada.gov.ba/bosanski/zakoni/2002/zakoni/72bos.htm>
- Law on Cultural Goods (Republika Srpska): <http://www.vladars.net/sr-SP-Cyrl/Vlada/Ministarstva/mk/Documents/Zakon%20o%20kulturnim%20dobrima.pdf>
- Law on Environmental Protection (Federation of BiH): <http://www.fbihvlada.gov.ba/bosanski/zakoni/2003/zakoni/33bos.htm>
- Law on Nature Protection (Federation of BiH): <http://www.fbihvlada.gov.ba/bosanski/zakoni/2003/zakoni/33bos.htm>

CROATIA

- Law on the Protection and Preservation of Cultural Goods (1999, amended in 2021): <https://www.zakon.hr/z/322/Zakon-o-za%C5%A1titi-i-o%C4%8Duvaniu-kulturnih-dobara>
- Environmental Protection Act (2007, amended in 2021): <https://www.zakon.hr/z/80/Zakon-o-za%C5%A1titi-okolika>
- Nature Protection Act (2005, amended in 2021): <https://www.zakon.hr/z/80/Zakon-o-za%C5%A1titi-prirode>

MONTENEGRO

- Law on the Protection of Cultural Property (2010, amended in 2020): <https://www.sluzbenilist.me/>
- Law on Environmental Protection (2008, amended in 2021): <https://www.sluzbenilist.me/>
- Nature Protection Law (2009, amended in 2021): <https://www.sluzbenilist.me/>

SERBIA

- Law on Cultural Property (2011, amended in 2019): https://www.paragraf.rs/propisi/zakon_o_kulturnim_dobrima.html

DELIVERABLE 7.5 POLICY BRIEF 1

- Law on Environmental Protection (2004, amended in 2021):
https://www.paragraf.rs/propisi/zakon_o_zastiti_zivotne_sredine.html
- Nature Protection Law (2009, amended in 2021):
https://www.paragraf.rs/propisi/zakon_o_zastiti_prirode.html

GERMANY

- Bavarian Monument Protection Act (Bayerisches Denkmalschutzgesetz):
<https://www.gesetze-bayern.de/Content/Document/BayDSchG>
- Federal Climate Change Act (Bundes-Klimaschutzgesetz, 2021):
<https://www.gesetze-im-internet.de/ksg/>
- Federal Nature Conservation Act (Bundesnaturschutzgesetz, BNatSchG):
https://www.gesetze-im-internet.de/bnatschg_2009/

AUSTRIA

- Austrian Monument Protection Act (Denkmalschutzgesetz, DMSG):
<https://www.ris.bka.gv.at/GeltendeFassung.wxe?Abfrage=Bundesnormen&Gesetzesnummer=10009238>
- Austrian Climate Protection Act (Klimaschutzgesetz, KSG):
<https://www.ris.bka.gv.at/GeltendeFassung.wxe?Abfrage=Bundesnormen&Gesetzesnummer=20009247>
- Austrian Nature Conservation Act (Naturschutzgesetz, NSG):
<https://www.ris.bka.gv.at/GeltendeFassung.wxe?Abfrage=Bundesnormen&Gesetzesnummer=10001704>

FRANCE

- Heritage Code (Code du Patrimoine):
<https://www.legifrance.gouv.fr/codes/id/LEGITEXT000006074236/>
- Environmental Code (Code de l'Environnement):
<https://www.legifrance.gouv.fr/codes/id/LEGITEXT000006074220/>
- Law for the Reconquest of Biodiversity, Nature, and Landscapes (2016):
<https://www.legifrance.gouv.fr/jorf/id/JORFTEXT000032884618>

MALTA

- Cultural Heritage Act (2002, amended in 2019):
<https://legislation.mt/eli/cap/445/eng>
- Climate Action Act (2015):
<https://legislation.mt/eli/act/2015/24/eng>

- Environmental Protection Act (2016):

<https://legislation.mt/eli/cap/549/eng>

REGISTER OF EU-LEVEL LAWS AND POLICIES RELATED TO CULTURAL HERITAGE PROTECTION AND CLIMATE CHANGE THREATS

TREATY ON THE FUNCTIONING OF THE EUROPEAN UNION (TFEU)

Article 167: Establishes the EU's role in supporting, coordinating, or supplementing the actions of member states in the conservation and safeguarding of cultural heritage of European significance. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A12012E%2FTXT>

EUROPEAN YEAR OF CULTURAL HERITAGE (2018)

This initiative highlighted the importance of cultural heritage for Europe's identity and promoted initiatives to protect and preserve it. It led to the European Framework for Action on Cultural Heritage, which emphasizes sustainable management of heritage sites. <https://ec.europa.eu/culture/cultural-heritage/european-year-cultural-heritage-2018>

CREATIVE EUROPE PROGRAMME (2021–2027)

This EU funding program supports the cultural and creative sectors, including projects focused on heritage conservation, restoration, and promotion. It includes the Culture Strand, which funds transnational cooperation projects involving heritage sites. <https://ec.europa.eu/culture/creative-europe>

EUROPEAN HERITAGE LABEL

This initiative identifies and promotes sites that symbolize European integration, history, and culture. While not a legal framework, it encourages the preservation and promotion of heritage sites across the EU. <https://ec.europa.eu/culture/cultural-heritage/initiatives-and-success-stories/european-heritage-label>

EUROPEAN GREEN DEAL (2019)

The European Green Deal is a comprehensive strategy to make the EU climate-neutral by 2050. It includes measures to protect natural and cultural heritage from climate change impacts, such as extreme weather events and pollution. https://ec.europa.eu/info/strategy/priorities-2019-2024/european-green-deal_en

EU CLIMATE ADAPTATION STRATEGY (2021)

This strategy emphasizes the need to protect cultural heritage from climate change by integrating heritage conservation into national and regional adaptation plans. It encourages the use of climate-resilient materials and techniques in restoration projects.

https://ec.europa.eu/clima/policies/adaptation/what_en

EU BIODIVERSITY STRATEGY FOR 2030

This strategy aims to protect and restore ecosystems, which often overlap with cultural heritage sites. It promotes the integration of biodiversity conservation and heritage protection.

https://ec.europa.eu/environment/strategy/biodiversity-strategy-2030_en

ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT ASSESSMENT (EIA) DIRECTIVE (2014/52/EU)

This directive requires member states to assess the environmental impact of projects that could affect cultural heritage sites, ensuring that development projects do not harm heritage assets.

<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32014L0052>

AIR QUALITY DIRECTIVES

Directive 2008/50/EC (Ambient Air Quality Directive): Sets limits on air pollutants like sulfur dioxide (SO₂) and nitrogen oxides (NO_x), which contribute to the deterioration of stone monuments.

<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32008L0050>

Industrial Emissions Directive (2010/75/EU): Regulates emissions from industrial activities that could harm cultural heritage sites.

<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32010L0075>

HORIZON EUROPE (2021–2027)

Horizon Europe is the EU's flagship research and innovation program. It includes funding for projects related to cultural heritage conservation, climate resilience, and sustainable development.

https://ec.europa.eu/info/horizon-europe_en

LIFE PROGRAMME

The LIFE Programme funds environmental and climate action projects, including those focused on protecting cultural heritage from climate change and pollution.

<https://ec.europa.eu/easme/en/life>

EUROPEAN STRUCTURAL AND INVESTMENT FUNDS (ESIF)

These funds support regional development, including the restoration and preservation of cultural heritage sites. Examples include:

EUROPEAN REGIONAL DEVELOPMENT FUND (ERDF):

Supports infrastructure projects, including heritage conservation.

https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/en/funding/erdf/

EUROPEAN SOCIAL FUND (ESF)

Funds training and capacity-building for heritage professionals.

<https://ec.europa.eu/esf/main.jsp?catId=62&langId=en>

EUROPEAN TERRITORIAL COOPERATION (INTERREG)

Interreg programs promote cross-border collaboration on cultural heritage projects, particularly in regions where heritage sites span multiple countries (e.g., the *stećci* in Southeastern Europe).

<https://www.interreg.eu/>

EUROPEAN HERITAGE DAYS

Coordinated by the Council of Europe and the European Commission, this initiative promotes cultural heritage awareness and encourages cross-border cooperation in heritage conservation.

<https://www.coe.int/en/web/cultural-routes/european-heritage-days>

VALLETTA CONVENTION (1992)

Officially known as the European Convention on the Protection of the Archaeological Heritage, this treaty requires signatory states to protect archaeological sites, including medieval stone monuments like the *stećci*.

<https://www.coe.int/en/web/culture-and-heritage/valletta-convention>

GRANADA CONVENTION (1985)

The Convention for the Protection of the Architectural Heritage of Europe emphasizes the need to protect historical monuments and sites, including stone heritage, from urban development and environmental threats.

<https://www.coe.int/en/web/culture-and-heritage/granada-convention>

FARO CONVENTION (2005)

The Framework Convention on the Value of Cultural Heritage for Society promotes the role of cultural heritage in sustainable development and encourages public participation in heritage conservation.

<https://www.coe.int/en/web/culture-and-heritage/faro-convention>

CIRCULAR ECONOMY ACTION PLAN (2020)

This plan promotes sustainable resource use and waste reduction, which can be applied to heritage conservation through the use of eco-friendly materials and techniques.

https://ec.europa.eu/environment/strategy/circular-economy-action-plan_en

EU WASTE FRAMEWORK DIRECTIVE (2008/98/EC)

Encourages the reuse and recycling of materials, including those used in heritage restoration projects.

<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32008L0098>

EU CIVIL PROTECTION MECHANISM

Provides support for disaster prevention and response, including measures to protect cultural heritage from natural disasters exacerbated by climate change. https://ec.europa.eu/echo/what/civil-protection/mechanism_en

SENDAI FRAMEWORK FOR DISASTER RISK REDUCTION (2015–2030)

While not an EU law, the EU supports this UN framework, which includes guidelines for protecting cultural heritage from disasters.

<https://www.unisdr.org/we/coordinate/sendai-framework>

DIGITAL EUROPE PROGRAMME (2021–2027)

Funds digital transformation projects, including the digitization of cultural heritage sites and the development of tools like 3D scanning and virtual reality for conservation and education. <https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/en/digital-europe-programme>

EU COPYRIGHT DIRECTIVE (2019/790)

Facilitates the digitization and online accessibility of cultural heritage materials while protecting intellectual property rights.

<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32019L0790>

REFERENCES

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2. ICOMOS-ISCS Illustrated Glossary on Stone Deterioration Patterns:
<https://www.icomos.org/en/resources/charters-and-texts>
3. IPCC Sixth Assessment Report: <https://www.ipcc.ch/assessment-report/ar6/>
4. EURO-CORDEX: <https://www.euro-cordex.net/>
5. ERA5-Land: <https://www.ecmwf.int/en/forecasts/datasets/reanalysis-datasets/era5>
6. Mendeley Data: <https://data.mendeley.com/>
7. STECCI Grant Agreement 101094822
8. Sketchfab: <https://sketchfab.com/>
9. The Green Cluster of Cultural Heritage: Climate Effects TeamEU funded projects Gerakis, Athanasios, Hemmelskamp, Jens Kowalczyk-Kedziora, Vyzika, Melpomeni European Geosciences Union General Assembly 2024 (EGU24), held 14-19 April, 2024 in Vienna, Austria. Online at <https://egu23.eu>, id.17228
10. STECCI Website: <https://steccihorizoneu.com/>
11. Resolution [CM/Res\(2013\)67](#) revising the rules for the award of the “Cultural Route of the Council of Europe” certification (*Adopted by the Committee of Ministers on 18 December 2013 at the 1187bis meeting of the Ministers’ Deputies*) <https://search.coe.int/cm?i=09000016805c69fe>
12. [Cultural Routes of the Council of Europe - Homepage - Cultural Routes](#)

STECCI WORKSHOP NOVI SAD, SERBIA, POLICY ROUNDTABLE AGENDA

<https://steccihorizonte.eu.com/stecci-workshop-and-the-policy-round-table-matica-srpska-2nd-3rd-december-2024-matice-srpske-1-novi-sad-serbia/>

STECCI WORKSHOP AND THE POLICY ROUND TABLE

Matica srpska

Matice srpske 1, Novi Sad, Serbia

December 2nd – 3rd, 2024

<https://steccihorizonte.eu.com/>

Chair: Prof Snežana Radulović (UNSPMF) & Mag Pamela Bartar (ZSI)

Monday 2nd December

9:30 – 10:00	Registration
10:00 - 10:10	Welcome word by Prof dr Goran Anačkov on behalf of Matice Srpska
10:10 - 10:20	Welcome word by Prof dr Nusret Drešković, STECCI project coordinator
10:20 - 10:30	Welcome word by Prof dr Snežana Radulović UNSPMF STECCI coordinator, WP7 Leader
10:20 - 10:30	Welcome word by Mag Pamela Bartar, ZSI STECCI coordinator, WP2 Leader
10:30 - 10:40	Welcome word by Dr Sandra Tinaj UDG STECCI co-coordinator, WP6 Leader
Session 1	Interproject coaching
10:40-11:10	STECCI in GREEN CLUSTER, Prof Nusret Drešković & Prof Snežana Radulović
11:10-11:20	Mag Maja Đorđević, Republički zavod za zaštitu spomenika kulture – Beograd / National institute for cultural heritage preservation, Belgrade
11:20-11:30	Dr Emina Zečević, National Museum in Belgrade, Serbia, Departement of medieval archaeology, Curator of Collections

11:30-11:40	Dr Milica Radišić, Institute of Archaeology Belgrade, Creative Europe project <i>StećakLand: Interpreting Art of Mysterious Medieval Stećak Tombstones through Virtual Reality</i> , coordinated by DIGI.BA, Bosnia & Herzegovina
11:40-12:00	Prof dr Monika Milosavljević Faculty of Philosophy, University of Belgrade, " <i>Unde venis?</i> " <i>Unravelling the enigma of the stećci tombstones</i> The European Research Council project coordinated by ZRC SAZU Institute of Archaeology, Slovenia
12:00-12:15	Coffee break
Session 2	Policy round table
12:15-13:15	Policy round table/Brainstorming
13:15-14:30	Stećci Model Exhibition by students of Bogdan Šuput High School of Art, moderator Dr Branka Radulović and Prof dr Maja Stojanović (UNSPMF) Coctail and Lunch break
14:30-15:00	Policy round table/Brainstorming
15:00-15:15	Mag Pamela Bartar & Gabor Szudi (ZSI) WP5 methodology
15:15-15:30	Introduction to Storytelling
15:30-18:00	Visiting the Petrovaradin Castle Museum
19:00	Dinner

Tuesday 3rd December

10:00 – 16:00	meeting point at Zorana Đinđića 2, Novi Sad (University campus, Rectorate) Escursion to stećci exhibit sites, Belgrade <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - site Ethnographic Museum Belgrade and - site Kalemegdan Castle Belgrade
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NEWSLETTER GREEN CLUSTER STECCI

STECCI in Green Cluster of Cultural Heritage

On December 1st, Geosystems Hellas launched the Green Cluster on Cultural Heritage, a collaborative initiative to protect cultural sites from the consequences of climate change and natural hazards, at the famous Byzantine Museum hybrid event.

Dr. Athanasios Gerakis, REA Project Advisor, the initiator and *Spiritus movens* of the Green Cluster in Cultural Heritage, introduced the collective perspectives of this initiative, highlighting the ultimate importance of collaboration and innovation. Ms. Irena Kowalczyk-Kedziora, Prof. Eythimios Bakogiannis, and Prof. Konstantinos Karantzas provided a powerful background remark emphasizing EU policy alignment and societal impact, the importance of cultural heritage and climate change in urban planning, and the role of the projects in advancing telecommunications and digital technologies.

Six EU projects – TRIQUETRA, THETIDA, MOXY, STECCI, GOGREEN, and RescueMe joined the united GREEN CLUSTER ON CULTURAL HERITAGE in pursuit of a common objective. Each project contributes unique knowledge and skills to mitigate the impending dangers that historic monuments encounter.

The initial assembly served as a representation of a collective dedication to conserve our cultural heritage in the face of ecological stressors. All project representatives were given the opportunity to present their consortium, the new technologies being implemented on their projects, and the resulting impact at the meeting.

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Prof Charalampos Ioannides, the TRIQUETRA (Toolbox for Assessing and Mitigating Climate Change Risks and Natural Hazards Threatening Cultural Heritage), project coordinator affiliated with the National Technical University of Athens, delivered an outstanding presentation concerning the implementation of emerging technologies and the broader implications of the TRIQUETRA Project.

Dr Aitziber Egusquiza, Senior researcher in Tecnalia Research and Innovation, delivered a presentation on innovative solutions implemented for the RescueME (Resilient Cultural Landscapes) project.

Dr Panagiotis Michalis, Senior Project Manager at the Institute of Communications and Computer Systems (ICCS) emphasized the vital achievements that the THETIDA (Technologies and Methods for Improved Resilience and Sustainable Preservation of Underwater and Coastal Cultural Heritage to Cope with Climate Change, Natural Hazards, and Environmental Pollution) project has made.

Prof Nusret Dreskovic, Project coordinator, Dean of the Faculty Science, Department of Geography, UNSA Sarajevo and Prof Saida Ibragic, Project manager, Department of Chemistry, provided both, the project presentation, and an analysis of the significant predicted impact of our STECCI (Stone Monument Ensembles and The Climate Change Impact) project.

Dr Katrien Keune, Professor by special appointment of Molecular Spectroscopy at the Faculty of Science of the University of Amsterdam (UvA) and Head of Science at the Rijksmuseum, elaborated on the revolutionary endeavours of the GoGreen (Green Strategies to Conserve the Past and Preserve the Future of Cultural Heritage) project.

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STECI
 on
**ARCHE Stakeholder Workshop organized by Rathgen-
 Forschungslabor Berlin, April 16–17, 2024.**

We are excited to share the highlights from the recent ARCHE Stakeholder Workshop, held in Berlin on April 16–17, 2024, chaired by Prof Stefan Simon. This pivotal event marked significant milestones for The Alliance for Research on Cultural Heritage in Europe (ARCHE), a dynamic three-year EU-funded Horizon project aimed at developing a comprehensive framework for Research and Innovation in Cultural Heritage across Europe. ARCHE, led by the Foundation des Sciences du Patrimoine (France), is a collaborative effort of 24 partners from 18 countries, including Germany. Since its kick-off in September 2022, ARCHE has been dedicated to fostering a holistic approach to preserving and advancing cultural heritage.

Chair Prof. Dr. Stefan Simon

As a part of the plenary session, Prof. Dr. Nusret Drešković and Prof. Dr. Snežana Radulović highlighted Work Package 2 as a pivotal part of the STECCI project, focusing on risk and vulnerability assessments of limestone monuments in line with a range of climate scenarios. The initiative aims to deepen the understanding of Climate Change Impact (CCI) on these historic structures across Europe. To do this, the team will evaluate the effects of differing climate types and air pollutants on the monuments selected in eight distinct countries. This assessment forms a critical component of the STECCI project's overall mission to protect these structures.

Looking towards the future, STECCI WP2 will assess the potential risks and vulnerabilities faced by limestone monuments up to the year 2100, over three varying time periods: near-term (2021–2040), medium-term (2041–2060), and long-term (2081–2100) all-encompassing Europe as a whole.

Additionally, STECCI WP2 is set to assemble all climatological aspects required for developing Preservation Guidelines. This innovative tact shines a light on groundbreaking preservation techniques essential in defending our heritage against environmental threats.

Authors:

Dr. Abdelrhman Fahmy and Prof. Dr. Snežana Radulović

We extend our gratitude to all participants for their valuable contributions and active engagement. Stay tuned for more updates as we move forward with our ambitious agenda to protect and innovate within the realm of cultural heritage.

For more detailed information about the workshop and future ARCHE initiatives, please visit <https://www.smb.museum/en/museums-institutions/rathgen-forschungslabor/home/> or contact Prof. Dr. Simon Stefan S.Simon@smb.spk-berlin.de.

Note: The Rathgen-Forschungslabor is believed to be the oldest museum laboratory in the world. It was founded in 1888 as the Chemistry Laboratory of the Königlische Museen zu Berlin and was later renamed in honour of its first director Friedrich Rathgen, a chemist who specialised in the conservation and analysis of historical objects.

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